

NERC

Data management plan required?	Yes (Outline followed by detailed DMP if successful in conjunction with NERC data centre)
RDM policy Link	https://nerc.ukri.org/research/sites/data/policy/data-policy/ https://nerc.ukri.org/research/sites/data/policy/datapolicy-guidance/
Definition of data	‘Digital and analogue items usually obtained by measurement, observation or modelling of the natural world and human impacts upon it, including all necessary calibration and quality control. This includes data generated through complex systems, such as information retrieval algorithms, data assimilation techniques and the application of models. Whereas, <i>Information Products</i> are created by adding a level of intellectual input that refines or adds value to data through interpretation and/or combination with other data. Model codes are not covered by this policy.’
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Submit appropriate metadata at the same time as the datasets. All data must also be accompanied by a data licence stating that users of the data must acknowledge the original investigator in any publication or work that has been derived from the data set in question. https://nerc.ukri.org/research/sites/data/dmp/dmp-template/
Required data repository	NERC Data Catalogue service
Time for data release	As soon as possible after end of data collection. This is defined as the point at which the data become available from an instrument of experiment (not the end of the project). Researchers are allowed an embargo period (maximum 2 years from end of data collection point), but this must be agreed before the start of the project.
Time for long-term storage of data	Minimum of 10 years after completion of research (20 years for major projects)
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	data@nerc.ac.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used:NERC Data policy <https://nerc.ukri.org/research/sites/data/policy/data-policy/>NERC Data policy guidance <https://nerc.ukri.org/research/sites/data/policy/datapolicy-guidance/>NERC data management planning <https://nerc.ukri.org/research/sites/data/dmp/>

NERC Full data management plan template

<https://nerc.ukri.org/research/sites/data/dmp/dmp-template/>**Accessed:** July 2018